

A Simple Extraction Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Arsenic in Water and Environmental Samples[†]

LATA CHERIAN, J. RAJU and V. K. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010

Manuscript received 27 April 1989, revised 22 January 1990, accepted 28 February 1990

A new reducing agent succinyldihydroxamic acid has been proposed for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of arsenic. The method is based on the reduction of yellow molybdoarsenic heteropoly acid with succinyldihydroxamic acid into molybdoarsenic blue. The blue coloured dye shows an absorption maxima at 780 nm in n-butanol. Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 0.02–0.14 ppm of arsenic. The method is free from several common interfering co-pollutants including phosphates. Various analytical parameters for colour development have been evaluated. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of arsenic in polluted water and environmental samples.

ARSENIC and its compounds in different forms are used in manufacture of drugs, glass, insecticides and textile printing and are present in their effluents¹⁻³. Arsenic is reported to be a potent carcinogenic and poisonous substance and its exposure may lead to laryngitis and gastrointestinal disturbances^{2,3}. The threshold limit value for arsenic is reported to be 0.5 mg m⁻³ (0.15 ppm)¹.

Various instrumental techniques are reported for the determination of arsenic⁴⁻¹². The most popular spectrophotometric method for the determination of arsenic is the molybdenum blue method which is based on the reduction of the yellow molybdoarsenic acid to molybdenum blue⁵⁻⁷.

In the present communication, a simple and sensitive method has been proposed for the determination of arsenic. The method is based on the reduction of yellow molybdoarsenic acid to molybdenum blue with a new reducing agent succinyldihydroxamic acid. The blue coloured dye shows absorption maxima at 780 nm in n-butanol. The method is free from several common interferences. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of arsenic in polluted water and environmental samples.

Experimental

A DMS 100 S Varian uv-visible spectrophotometer was used.

A 1 mg ml⁻¹ stock arsenic solution was prepared by dissolving sodium arsenite in demineralised water and working standard was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock. A 2.5% aqueous ammonium molybdate solution was prepared after pre-heating.

Succinyldihydroxamic acid (SDHA) was prepared by the condensation of diethyl succinate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride at 0^o¹⁴, m.p. 164–66^o; its 0.1% aqueous solution was prepared. 10 N sulphuric acid was used. All reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the sample containing 1–7 µg of arsenic (0.02–0.14 ppm) was added ammonium molybdate (2 ml). The acidity of the solution was adjusted to 2.5–3.5 N with sulphuric acid and then SDHA (1 ml) was added and the volume made upto 50 ml. The mixture was kept on a boiling water-bath for ~5 min till the development of blue colour, indicating the presence of arsenic. The contents were kept for 10 min for complete colour development. The solution was then extracted with n-butanol (2 × 5 ml). The blue coloured extract was measured at 780 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Effect of acidity: An acidity range of 2.5–3.5 N sulphuric acid was required for complete reduction of heteropoly acid to molybdenum blue. Higher acidity showed a decrease in absorbance values. In lower acidity, the blank also gave colour and phosphorus also interfered.

Time and temperature: At least 5 min time was required for complete reduction on a boiling water-bath, and cooling for another 10 min for full colour development. The stability of the blue coloured complex was found to be 6 h.

Effect of reagent concentration: At least 2 ml of 2.5% ammonium molybdate and 0.5 ml of 0.1% SDHA were required for complete colour reaction.

[†]Paper was accepted for presentation at Pittsburg Conference on Analytical Chemistry held in Atlanta, 1989, in Liquid Chromatography Section (Paper no. 187).

Excess reagents however did not show any adverse effect.

Beer's law, sensitivity and reproducibility : Beer's law was found valid in the range of 1–7 $\mu\text{g}/50\text{ ml}$ of arsenic (0.02–0.14 ppm) (Fig. 1). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be 4.30×10^5 (± 100) $\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0002 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.017 and 15.6% for 1 $\mu\text{g}/50\text{ ml}$ arsenic solution

and ± 0.018 and 2.25% for 7 $\mu\text{g}/50\text{ ml}$ arsenic solution analysed over a period of 7 days.

Effect of solvent extraction : Of the various solvents studied n-butanol was found to be most sensitive for the extraction. In isoamyl alcohol colour was less stable and extraction was incomplete in n-hexane and isopropanol.

Effect of foreign species : Phosphates, the most expected interferent, does not interfere upto 800-fold excess in the acidity range of 2.5–3.5 N sulphuric acid at which arsenic has been determined. Its interference when present in excess can be removed by extracting molybdophosphoric acid with isoamyl alcohol¹⁰; under these conditions the arsenic is not extracted. Interference of silicon can be removed by extracting arsenic from the alcoholic solution of the sample with isoamyl alcohol and silicon remains in the aqueous phase⁶. Interference of copper can be avoided by extracting it with cupferron and chloroform before distillation. The interference of compounds present as a major constituents in biological samples were also carried out and the method was found to be free from the interference of glucose, urea, bicarbonate, sulphide, citrate, uric acid and amino acids. Interferences by lipids and creatinine could not be checked due to the non-availability of the compounds and are not likely to interfere. The tolerance limits (amount in ppm in parenthesis which may vary by 2%) of foreign species in 3 $\mu\text{g}/50\text{ ml}$ (0.06 ppm) arsenic concentration are as follows: Na, K, chloride, sulphate, phosphate and nitrate (800); Sr^{II} (masked with 1 ml of 10% EDTA) and nitrite (600); Ca^{II} (masked with 1 ml of 10% EDTA); Cd^{II} and bromide (500); Pb^{II} (masked with 1 ml of 10% EDTA), V, Sb^{III} , Ni^{II} and fluoride (400); Mn^{II}

Fig. 1 Calibration curve for the determination of arsenic.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION IN WATER AND ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES*

Sample	Set No.	As originally found by proposed method μg	As originally found by reported method μg	As added μg	Total As found by proposed method μg	Total As found by reported method μg	% Recovery by proposed method	% Recovery by reported method
Tap water ^a	1	—	—	3	2.98	2.96	99.3	98.6
	2	—	—	3	2.99	2.96	99.6	98.6
	3	—	—	3	2.98	2.95	99.3	98.3
River water ^a	1	6.10	5.89	3	9.09	8.87	99.9	96.4
	2	8.62	8.58	3	11.61	11.56	99.9	99.8
	3	11.55	11.49	3	14.53	14.46	99.8	99.7
Effluent water ^a (steel industry)	1	2.54	2.52	3	5.53	5.49	99.8	99.4
	2	6.08	6.02	3	9.07	8.99	99.8	99.6
	3	13.09	13.01	3	16.06	15.97	99.8	99.7
Soil ^b	1	2.32	2.29	3	5.30	5.23	99.6	98.8
	2	5.03	4.87	3	8.00	7.79	99.6	98.9
	3	10.36	10.32	3	13.35	13.25	99.9	99.4
Dust ^b	1	4.25	4.23	3	7.24	7.19	99.8	99.4
	2	5.80	5.74	3	8.78	8.69	99.7	99.4
	3	3.20	3.17	3	6.16	6.11	99.3	99.0

* Mean of 3 replicate analyses.

^aAmount of sample=1 ml;

^bAmount of sample=0.1 g; the samples were collected from different regions.

(masked with 1 ml of 10% EDTA), Hg^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cr^{III}, carbonate and sulphide (200); Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} (both masked with 1 ml of 10% sodium potassium tartarate), Al^{III}, Se^{IV} and Ni^{II} (100); Cu^{II} (separated with cupferron).

Application :

In tap, river and effluent water : The river water sample receiving effluents from a fertiliser factory and effluent water sample from a steel industry were filtered prior to analysis. Suitable aliquots of the samples were taken and analysed by the proposed method. Since the tap water contained no arsenic synthetic samples were prepared by adding known amount of arsenic and then analysed. The results are shown in Table 1.

In soil : Finely ground soil sample (0.1 g) was fortified with known amount of arsenic and taken in a nickel crucible and digested as reported earlier^{1,6}. Aliquots of this treated sample were analysed by the proposed method. Dust samples near a steel industry were also treated similarly and analysed. The results are shown in Table 1.

In urine and serum : The samples of serum and urine were deproteinated with trichloroacetic acid as reported^{1,6} and filtered. Aliquots were then used for the determination of arsenic by proposed and reported method using sodium metavanadate*. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF ARSENIC IN URINE AND SERUM

Sample*	As found by proposed method** µg	As found by reported method** µg
Urine	1.25 ± 0.15	1.22 ± 0.11
	1.64 ± 0.21	1.63 ± 0.22
	1.85 ± 0.35	1.85 ± 0.30
Serum	1.77 ± 3.31	1.75 ± 0.51
	2.05 ± 0.27	2.05 ± 0.42
	2.76 ± 0.41	2.73 ± 0.75

*Amount of sample = 10 ml. **Average ± standard deviation of 7 analyses.

Conclusion : The method is found to be more sensitive than many of the existing spectrophotometric methods⁴⁻⁹ (Table 3). The stability of the dye formed, non-interference of common ions and solvent extraction make the present method more advantageous. The method can also be effectively applied to environmental samples.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS

Sl. no.	Reagent	λ _{max}	Range of determination ppm
1.	Ammonium molybdate + sodium metavanadate ^a	460	1-80
2.	Ammonium molybdate + hydrazine sulphate ^b	725	0.4-2
3.	Ammonium molybdate + stannous chloride ^c	332	0.3-1.5
4.	Ammonium vanadate + crystal violet ^d	545	0.2-0.8
5.	Silverdiethylthiocarbamate + piperidine ^e	500	0.04-0.8
6.	Ammonium molybdate + ethyl violet ^f	555	0.03-0.24
7.	Ammonium molybdate + SDHA ^g	780	0.02-0.14

^aRef. 4. ^bRef. 5. ^cRef. 6. ^dRef. 7. ^eRef. 8. ^fRef. 9. ^gPresent method.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur, for facilities. Two of the authors (L.C. and J.R.) are grateful to the University for providing Fellowships.

References

1. F. A. PATTY, 'Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology', Interscience, New York, 1963, Vol. II, p. 871.
2. M. E. JACOBS, "Analytical Toxicology of Industrial Inorganic Poisons", Interscience, New York, 1967, Vol. 22, p. 368.
3. "Standard method for the Examination of Water and Waste Water", 14th. ed., APHA, 1975, p. 282.
4. D. K. GULLSTROM and M. G. MELLON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 1809.
5. A. L. CHANEY and H. J. MAGNUSON, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1940, **12**, 691.
6. A. D. MICHAEL and I. B. ROGERS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1381.
7. N. JIE and S. WANG, *Haaxue Shiji*, 1987, **9**, 175 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1988, **40**, 50).
8. P. K. GUPTA and P. K. GUPTA, *J. Inst. Chem. (Calcutta)*, 1986, **58**, 103.
9. F. MENG and X. YUAN, *Fenxi Huaxue Shiji*, 1986, **14**, 809 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1987, **49**, 9H 54).
10. P. PAKALNS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1969, **47**, 225.
11. C. WADLEIN and M. G. MELLON, *Analyst*, 1952, **77**, 708.
12. B. S. CHANA and N. J. SMITH, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **197**, 177.
13. J. P. ARNOLD and R. M. JOHNSON, *Talanta*, 1968, **16**, 1191.
14. A. CHOUBE and V. K. GUPTA, *Analyst*, 1984, **109**, 99.
15. H. ALMOND, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 1766.
16. W. N. ALDRIDGE, *Analyst*, 1944, **69**, 262.